

ANALYSIS OF VIEWS ON THE FORMATION OF YOUTH LEGAL CULTURE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the level of the legal system in which the legal culture is established in the society, the public’s awareness of this legal system, the citizens’ respect for the law, the implementation of legal norms and the manifestation of the level of obedience to the law.

Key words: Human value, legal culture, legal consciousness, society, feeling, legal education, respect, mentality.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the age-old traditions, traditions, language, religion, and spirit of our people, legal culture serves to instill in our minds the feelings of enlightenment and truth, such as honesty and faith, justice and legality, high respect and attention to people, and patience. From this point of view, it is vital to raise the legal culture that directs people’s thoughts and worldviews to work selflessly for the development of our country. Raising legal consciousness and legal culture in society is one of the most important conditions for ensuring the rule of law and strengthening legitimacy.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language: "1. Culture - (Arabic - civilization) a set of achievements of society in production, social, spiritual and educational life. 2. The level of such achievements achieved by a social group, class or people in a certain period. 3. Education, education, intelligence, enlightenment. 4. Conditions that meet the requirements of a civilized person.

The great thinkers of the East are Abu Nasr Farabi, Musa Al-Khorazmi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Najmuddin Kubra, Imam al-Bukhari, al-Tirmizi, Ahmad Yassavi, Mirza Ulug’bek, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navai, Boborahim Mashrab, Mirza Bedil, Mahtumquli. , Abay, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdulla Avloni, Ahmad Donish, etc., specifically focused on the issues of law, justice, and obedience to the law.

Aspects of legal culture related to the field of jurisprudence, legal scholars of our country: A.A. Azizkhodjaev, S.M. Adilkhodjaeva, H.B. Boboev, Sh.I. Jalilov, Z.M. Islamov, Analyzed by H.T. Odilkoriev, A.Kh. Saidov.

RESULTS

During the years of independence in Uzbekistan, special attention was paid to the processes of developing youth political culture, among other areas. Especially in recent years, all conditions have been created in our country for young people to grow up well in all aspects. "We will resolutely continue the state policy on youth without deviation. Not only will we continue, but we will raise this policy to the highest level that the times demand today as our highest priority. We mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that our young people can be independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field, and be happy." Today, scientific research of the processes of development of youth political culture in Uzbekistan and development of modern mechanisms for its further improvement and development is one of the most urgent tasks facing our society and, moreover, our state.

DISCUSSION

A deep analysis of various approaches and points of view put forward by experts who have studied the sphere of legal life of society, the problems of raising human legal consciousness, legal and political culture in one way or another is required. Legal culture is determined by the level of legal consciousness and legal-political culture of people living in a certain community, legal norms and legal activities (law creation, law enforcement, law enforcement activities). Its basis is knowledge about law and its interpretations, as well as efforts in accordance with it, all of which are directly related to the level of legal and political culture of citizens in society.

Jean-Jacques Rousseau, a French intellectual, promoted a scientific approach to legal culture and laws. He believes that freedom and equality are the main conditions for the development of human legal culture. "For the same reason, the exigencies of the situation always tend to destroy equality, and the force of laws must always tend to preserve it."

The system of general and social worldviews of society members includes political, legal and other types of consciousness. In turn, problems of legal and ecological legal consciousness have always been an important aspect in the formation of social and individual consciousness in society. At this point, it should be emphasized that when we begin to analyze the categories of legal and ecological legal consciousness as a form of social consciousness, we can see that there are different interpretations of it in the views of the authors conducting scientific research on the

topic and in different sources. In particular, in the opinion of the legal scientist E.H. Khalilov, who conducted monographic research on the issue of legal consciousness, "legal consciousness means understanding the law. Legal consciousness is a part of social consciousness and therefore it is influenced by philosophical, ideological and political views.

There is a need for young people with a certain legal awareness and culture in the establishment of a legal state and civil society, but legal and political culture does not arise by itself, it is necessary to form it in our youth from early childhood with the help of social institutions.

The dimension of legal culture is interrelated with the level of development of the legal system, popularization of social, legal and political institutions, level of literacy of the population, legal consciousness and legal ideology in the society.

"The level of legal culture of the society is determined not by the number of adopted laws, but by the implementation of these laws at all levels. In this important work, it is of particular importance to educate people to have deep respect for laws and regulatory legal documents.

Because legal norms live and come true only if they are absorbed in people's minds and act through them. Only through laws and improved legal administration, it is possible to educate a legal activist with a high legal status, whose rights and freedoms are legally guaranteed.

SUMMARY

The political culture of citizens arises and develops mainly as a result of two: external and internal influences. External influence is a type of influence that arises in society through the activities of ideologies, ideological institutions and state bodies, explaining and reminding citizens of laws throughout their lives, while internal influence is the process of awakening the inner will and "I" formed as a result of external influence. The interrelationship of political culture with ideology and ideological categories is evident in the process of forming internal influence among citizens.

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